

Neutron resilience of flexible perovskite solar cells using PTAA-derived hole transport layers

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ABSTRACT

Flexible perovskite solar cells hold promise of being an enabling technology for space missions: by reducing the encumbrance and weight of the payload's power system, launch costs can be minimized. The increased interest, however, must be accompanied by thorough testing under a broad range of space-related sources of degradation, and investigation of their effects on the layer stack. In this work, we studied the resilience against atmospheric neutron radiation (<800 MeV) of flexible devices employing two different hole transporting materials: a commercial PTAA, and a PTAA-based in-house synthesized polymer. After $5 \cdot 10^9$ particles/cm² irradiation, 380 times higher than the yearly fast neutron fluence in Low Earth Orbit, our devices show good stability, with efficiency losses below 20%. Further investigation by light intensity-dependent JV scans, hyperspectral photoluminescence microscopy, X-ray diffraction, X-ray reflectivity and Atomic Force Microscopy, reveals that the neutron radiation mainly affects the perovskite/hole transport layer interface, to a different extent depending on the material. This work confirms that accelerated stress testing is an important tool to determine the feasibility of this technology for space applications, and provides insights on the damages caused by atmospheric neutrons which will help inform future decisions for the fabrication of space-resilient flexible perovskite solar cells.

1. Introduction

Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) appear promising for many terrestrial applications thanks to factors such as a power conversion efficiency (PCE) above 26%, [1] solution-based manufacturing, and tunable bandgap, [2] but also show promise for space applications.

The investigation of PSCs for use in space began in 2015, when Miyazawa *et al.* found their $3\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{I}+\text{PbCl}_2$ perovskite solar cells irradiated with 10^{16} electrons/cm² retained 93% of their initial efficiency, whereas a traditional III-V solar cell would retain only about 75% under the same conditions. [3] Further irradiation experiments have confirmed this high resilience of PSCs to electron [4] [5] [6] and proton [4] [5] [6] [7] [8] radiation, consolidating the interest for space applications of this technology.

As the focus broadened to other damage sources present in the space environment, such as atomic oxygen, [9] [10] vacuum, [11] [12] [13] or gamma radiation, [14] [15] [16] [17] particle radiation aging tests have also started to include resilience to neutrons. Unlike protons and electrons, neutrons are not electrically charged, and therefore do not directly cause ionization effects in an irradiated material.

The mass of a neutron however is still significant enough to cause elastic collisions with atoms in the targeted material, [18] which can displace nuclei, leaving defects in the lattice. [19] Thus, neutrons can be associated with degradation of the photovoltaic performance of a device, a behaviour that has been observed in simulations [20] and experimentally. [21] Characterizing the extent of this damage in PSCs for space applications is therefore important, as neutrons are present in various space environments, such as around spacecrafts, whether in orbit [22] or interplanetary travel, [23] or in other planets atmospheres. [24] In all these cases, the interaction between solar radiation and encountered atoms (in the atmosphere or in a spacecraft's body) produces so-called atmospheric neutrons with energies up to hundreds of MeV. Neutrons in this spectrum are therefore representative of a variety of extreme environments within space applications, and can be used as a relevant source for accelerated degradation tests.

For space applications, flexible solar cells are more attractive than their rigid counterparts not only because of their increased specific power ($\text{W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), but also because of their reduced packing size when folded or rolled, as is the current practice for NASA [25] [26] and the International Space Station. [27] The first fully thin-film PV array, the Lightweight Integrated Solar Array and anTenna (LISA-T) using a polymeric-encapsulated Copper Indium Gallium Selenide array on a polyimide substrate to deliver 10.5% PCE (under AM0 illumination at 25 °C), has undergone relevant testing for low Earth orbit missions, and regardless the low efficiency compared with the III-V solar cells, has been deemed acceptable for short missions (~2 years). [28]

Despite this opportunity for flexible devices and in striking contrast with the abundance of reports on rigid PSCs, [3] [4] [5] [6] [7] [8] [9] [29] [30] [31] [32] [33] [34] [35] [36] [37] [38] few reports have investigated the resilience to particle radiation of flexible perovskite solar cells (f-PSC), [39] [40] [41] which are potentially cheaper than other technologies [42] and can reach higher specific power. [43] More in detail, no other work aside from our 2021 study was found on the atmospheric neutron irradiation of f-PSCs. Unlike protons and electrons, neutrons are still under represented in literature, despite being an important source of degradation in space, possibly due to the rarity of beamlines providing atmospheric neutrons. [44]

Aside from the outlined technical and operational advantages in space applications, f-PSCs can also be considered for their potential sustainable production thanks to the possibility to implement

scalable, low temperature, continuous printing processes.[45] This might be crucial for short-term low Earth orbit missions, which continue to grow in number,[46] [47] and will have to face the question of sustainable use of the space environment.[47] [48] [49] [50]

Here, we present the effects of atmospheric neutrons on the performance of f-PSC employing two different Hole Transport Layers (HTLs): a commercial PTAA and an in-house modified PTAA-like polymer, herein denoted as P1. Our proposed polymeric HTL sees the chemical insertion of a phenothiazine moiety to the main PTAA backbone. The reasoning behind this relates to its chemically stable and tuneable nature, and as such, has already shown promising nature as organic HTLs in f-PSC. Above all, its cheap commercial price coupled with higher yielding synthetic protocols allows to potentially reduce the cost of the device, an aspect that is very critical for space programs.[51] Furthermore, P1 was selected as viable alternative to PTAA in space application due to its extremely high thermal inertness and photochemically stability as well as the possibility to form stable radical-cations due to its electron rich atoms (nitrogen and sulphur) and conjugated π electronic structure. Additionally, the sulphur atom present in the phenothiazine scaffold has shown potential neutron scavenging properties,[40] via the stabilization of radical cation formation,[52] which could help to improve the neutron resilience associated to the HTL layer. Moreover P1 was observed to have larger crystal coherence lengths, which could further help its resilience against radiation compared other more amorphous candidates such as PTAA.[52][53][52][54] Finally P1 is soluble in THF, an environmentally friendly solvent, which allows for a more sustainable production of PSCs compared to PTAA, commonly employing the toxic and hazardous toluene.

We irradiated the cells with $5 \cdot 10^9$ neutrons/cm², with a spectrum matching that of atmospheric neutrons in a fast neutron regime (>1 MeV).[44] This experimental fluence is approximately 380 times higher than the yearly natural fast neutrons fluence if scaled to low orbits satellites. [22] [55] To estimate the loss of photovoltaic performance, we performed current density – voltage (JV) scans under simulated sunlight before and after the irradiation. To further characterize the devices, we recorded light intensity-dependant JV scans, and hyperspectral photoluminescence microscopy. The morpho-structural characterization [56] [57] [58] [59] was carried out applying complementary techniques such as X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), X-Ray Reflectivity (XRR), and Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM). Finally hyperspectral photoluminescence microscopy were performed on half-stack samples consisting only of PET/ITO/electron transport layer (ETL)/perovskite.

We found that all tested devices present good atmospheric-neutron resilience, losing no more than 20% of their initial power conversion efficiency after the irradiation. Furthermore, hyperspectral photoluminescence maps of the devices reveal that atmospheric neutrons do not significantly affect non-radiative recombinations in the devices, while short-circuit current measures at different light intensities show more significant changes to the charge extraction dynamics of the devices.

2. Results and discussion

We fabricated f-PSCs with a direct (n-i-p) architecture, based on a SnO₂ transparent ETL, a triple cation double halide absorber layer, namely Cs_{0.06}FA_{0.78}MA_{0.16}Pb(I_{0.84}Br_{0.16})₃, an HTL and a gold top electrode

Figure 1a). As HTL, we compared a commercial PTAA, as the reference material with our in-house synthesized P1 which differs from PTAA for the presence of a phenothiazine unit specifically inserted into the polymeric scaffold with a 1:1 molar ratio with the triarylamine unit. The triarylamine unit also sees a modified methyl substitution, with a single methyl group in the para position, which improves structural packing compared to conventionally, tri-substituted PTAA.[51]

Three devices for each HTL were fabricated and encapsulated by covering the active area with kapton tape (Daokai). Each HTL batch was divided into a control set and a set for irradiation tests. The use of a non-irradiated control set is necessary to disentangle ageing effects related to atmospheric exposure and handling of the cells, as highlighted by Kirmani et al. .[60]

Figure

1b shows the JV scans under AM1.5G illumination of the champion devices for both P1 and PTAA cells, with a PCE of 11.9% and 15.3%, respectively (average values of 12.7% for PTAA, and 9.2% for P1, as estimated by reverse JV scans). The cells share similar open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) values: average of 1.01 V for P1, and 1.06 V for PTAA; however, the devices employing the in-house synthesized P1 suffer from shunt and series resistive losses, recorded also in dark JV scans (Figure 1S) which limit the fill factor (FF).

Figure 1: a) Schematic illustration of the cell stack employed in this work, alongside the chemical structure of the tested HTLs. b) JV scans of the best cells prepared for each tested HTL, the plot's key reports the PCE extracted from each scan

After the characterization, all the devices were sealed in a nitrogen filled bag. The samples destined for irradiation were brought to the ISIS Neutron and Muon Source (Didcot, UK), and irradiated in the ChipIR beamline with a target fluence of $5 \cdot 10^9$ neutrons/cm² while the control devices were kept in the irradiation facility stored in the dark. The fluence was chosen based on our previous experience with atmospheric neutron irradiation of n-i-p f-PSC, in which we recorded performance losses already at 10^9 neutrons/cm², and more pronounced degradation at 10^{10} neutrons/cm²; a fluence of $5 \cdot 10^9$ neutrons/cm² would therefore be comparable with our previous experiment, and can be expected to induce measurable degradation in our devices. The devices were kept under a nitrogen environment at all times they were not being measured.

Figure 2 shows the percent change of the a) open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}), b) short-circuit current density (J_{sc}), c) fill-factor (FF), and d) power conversion efficiency (PCE) of the irradiated and control devices, for both P1 and PTAA-based cells.

With regards to radiation hardness of flexible substrates for PSC, PET is the only material tested so far, and has been found to degrade only minimally under protons [7] [39] and atmospheric neutrons. [40] This is a stark difference to the common glass substrates used for rigid cells, which darken when irradiated by protons and electrons, requiring researchers to estimate a decoupling of the ageing of the cell from that of the substrate [7] or fabricate their cells on space-grade substrates.[3] [60] This makes f-PSC not only application-relevant for space missions, but an architecture that can be easily tested on the ground.

As our PET/ITO substrate has shown to retain large part of its optical transmittance under atmospheric neutrons,[40] we were able to accurately estimate the photovoltaic parameters of the devices before and after the irradiation directly from the forward and reverse JV scans of the devices under AM1.5G illumination.

Figure 2: Percent change of the photovoltaic parameters of the devices expressed as $100 \cdot (P_{\text{after}} - P_{\text{before}}) / P_{\text{before}}$, where P is the parameter. Yellow bars show changes in the non-irradiated control devices after the storage period (in dark and nitrogen atmosphere), while dark blue bars show devices after atmospheric neutron irradiation. a-b) changes in the open-circuit voltage and short-circuit current density (respectively), c-d) changes in fill-factor and power conversion efficiency (respectively)

The results confirm the overall good radiation hardness for f-PSC: the P1-based devices do not show any loss in PCE, and the PTAA-based cells lose around 20% of their initial PCE (Figure 2d). We note that the control devices do not show significant degradation of their photovoltaic performance, indicating that any changes observed in the irradiated devices are indeed mostly attributable to the neutron bombardment, rather than storage or shipping conditions.

We can see from Figure 2 that for all parameters, there is little change between irradiated and control P1 devices, whereas the PTAA-based devices suffer slightly more degradation due to neutrons. In particular, the FF remains on average within 5% of its initial value for both P1 and PTAA control devices, while for the irradiated devices P1 gains 3% and the PTAA loses 15% of their initial FF. Such FF decrement is the main cause of PCE loss for the irradiated PTAA devices, suggesting that resistive losses might be the cause of performance degradation for PTAA-based devices. Nevertheless, it is important to note that for each HTL, the average FF change of the control devices remains within one standard deviation of the irradiated ones.

The J_{SC} of P1-based devices sees on average a 5% decrement, for both irradiated and control devices. Control PTAA devices on the other hand lose only 2% of their initial J_{SC} , while the irradiated counterparts lose about 7%.

Interestingly, the V_{OC} remains extremely stable, with no sign of degradation across all sets of devices, which suggests the neutron irradiation does not increase non-radiative losses in the devices.[56] [57]. Furthermore, it's worth noting that both control and irradiated P1 devices show an improvement in V_{OC} ($+5 \pm 1\%$, and $+4 \pm 1\%$, respectively), whereas for the cells based on PTAA only the control set showed a small improvement of $\sim 2 \pm 1\%$, compared to the irradiated cells, whose V_{OC} remained unchanged ($+0 \pm 1\%$).

To further analyze the observed J_{SC} behaviour, we characterized the cells under a range of light intensities (Figure 2s). For PSCs the J_{SC} is linearly dependent on light intensity, however bimolecular recombination, space charge limitations and series resistance can cause the dependence to be sub-linear.[61] [62] Analysing the dependence of J_{SC} to light illumination also allows us to attribute changes seen in J_{SC} under 1 sun strictly to changes in charge extraction dynamics in the full device, rather than changes in the absorption of the bulk of the perovskite.

To quantify the sublinear dependence of the devices, the J_{SC} values were fitted to a power law expressed as $J_{sc(\Phi)} = C \cdot \Phi^\alpha$ where Φ is the light intensity, and C and α are fitting parameters. A perfectly linear current-intensity dependence would therefore be represented with an α value of 1, while values less than 1 denote the presence of the aforementioned charge extraction non-idealities.

Table 1: Parameters resulting from a power-law fit of the J_{sc} dependence from light intensity, extracted from JV scans performed up to 3 sun white LED illumination

	P1	PTAA
	α	α
Before - Control	0.94 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.01
After - Control	0.91 ± 0.07	0.97 ± 0.02
$\Delta\alpha$	-0.03	0.01
Before - Irradiated	0.96 ± 0.04	0.92 ± 0.03
After - Irradiated	0.95 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.03
$\Delta\alpha$	-0.01	0.00

Table 1 summarizes the average result of this analysis: initially, all samples have values of α close to 1, with the PTAA-based devices generally outperforming the P1, similarly to what is seen under 1-sun illumination.[51] After the irradiation experiment, the α values in the control devices remain close to their initial value, with the P1 devices suffering a slightly larger decrement ($\Delta\alpha = -0.03$) than the PTAA counterparts ($\Delta\alpha = +0.01$). The irradiated P1 samples however show an even lesser reduction of their average α value ($\Delta\alpha = -0.01$) compared to their controls, while the α value of PTAA-based devices remains unchanged ($\Delta\alpha = 0.00$). We note that all the changes in α recorded lie within 1 standard deviation of the mean α values after the experiment.

This analysis shows that the irradiated samples incur into minimal degradation of the J_{SC} dependence to illumination intensity. Importantly, even for P1 samples, that show the largest loss of α , the difference between irradiated and control sets is negligible, suggesting that the neutron irradiation is less damaging to the cells than the effects of storage, shipping, and handling. It is

important to note that the latter might obfuscate the absolute impact of neutron-induced damages in P1-based devices, therefore future studies will require optimized control storage and shipping conditions, in order to more accurately compare the effects of neutrons on the two different HTLs. Nevertheless in both cases the impact of atmospheric neutrons is still small and not destructive for the solar cells, even when measuring at illumination intensities up to 3 suns.

Figure 3s and Figure 4s show the trend of average V_{OC} against light intensity, as well as ideality factor (n) extracted as a logarithmic fit of the V_{OC} -Suns curve (Figure 3s) and as the slope of V_{OC} against the natural logarithm of light intensity (Figure 4s), as presented in literature[63] [64] When looking at the ideality factor fitted in the low intensity region (< 1 Sun) of the V_{OC} -Suns curve (fit values reported in Figure 3s), no significant difference is found before and after the experiment for the irradiated samples, while the control devices show a slight decrease of n . We note that all values of n found are greater than 2, indicating that below 1 Sun the V_{OC} behavior is dominated by shunts, [65] [7] and it is therefore important not to limit this analysis to the fitted values, but to also show the evolution of n across illumination intensities. The light intensity dependence of n reveals clear differences between the two HTLs: for P1 based cells, n remains constant ($n \approx 2$) for most of the investigated light intensity range, with a drop-off in values due to a saturation of V_{OC} at the highest illumination intensities, the ideality factor in the PTAA counterparts on the other hand is more strongly dependent on illumination, with a shunt-dominated region under low intensity ($n \approx 3$) and a sharp decline ($n < 1$) above 1 Sun due to a stronger saturation of V_{OC} . Such saturation of V_{OC} has been linked in previous studies to uneven thickness of HTL and incomplete coverage of the perovskite surface[66]and could provide a possible explanation for the slightly lower resilience to atmospheric neutrons of PTAA compared to P1.

To more thoroughly probe the effects of irradiation on V_{OC} , we performed hyperspectral photoluminescence (PL) microscopy on full devices and ITO/SnO₂/perovskite half-stacks. This technique provided spatially resolved absolute-intensity PL spectra of the same region of interest before and after the irradiation. The local PL spectra were then fit to the generalised Planck law to obtain the quasi-Fermi level splitting (QFLS), a parameter used to assess voltage losses due to nonradiative recombination. Being a purely optical measurement, this technique enables us to determine the local voltage losses for full devices as well as half-stacks, and therefore whether the observed V_{OC} trends are due to interactions with the HTL or the stability of the perovskite's bulk and buried interface. Furthermore, the microscopic spatial resolution is a key tool in imaging sites of local degradation that could be missed in a macroscopic measurement.

Figure 3: Microscopic quasi-Fermi level splitting maps of ITO/SnO₂/perovskite samples showing consistent regions of interest under illumination from 530 nm and 617 nm LEDs. a)-b) Map of a non-irradiated control sample, stored in nitrogen and in the dark, before and after the storage period, respectively. c)-d) Map of a sample before and after the irradiation, respectively.

Figure 3 shows the QFLS maps for

ITO/SnO₂/perovskite half-stacks before and after the irradiation or control treatment. In both cases, the spatial features and absolute QFLS values are largely unchanged across the maps, with full statistics summarized in Figure 5s. This is in line with our observation that V_{OC} remains stable in the full devices regardless of HTL, again suggesting that the neutron irradiation does not introduce significant nonradiative recombination pathways in the perovskite or its surface.[67] [68] The resilience in QFLS seen here is in contrast to conventional III-V cells, where similar microscopy experiments have revealed losses in the local luminescence efficiency, V_{OC} , and PCE after proton irradiation.[29]

XRD analysis of complete cells and PET/ITO/SnO₂/perovskite/HTL intermediates was performed before and after neutron irradiation, in order to evaluate the active materials structural stability.

Figure 4 shows the XRD patterns of the complete devices, while the intermediates are shown in Figure 6s, ruling out the PET contribution. Indeed, when perovskite films are deposited on PET/ITO substrates the XRD patterns are typically dominated by the intense signals located in the range $21^\circ < 2\theta < 29^\circ$ assigned to (110) and (100) PET reflections,[69] as reported in Figure 7s.

The crystalline nature of the perovskite films is clearly revealed in both pristine intermediates: the strong sharp signals located around 14° , 20° , 31.7° , 34.8° , 40.4° and 43° (labelled by black circles) are assigned to perovskite α -phase.[2][70][71] Furthermore, both PbI_2 signal (labelled by black triangles) accordingly to JCD 01-073-0591[72]) and $\text{FABr-PbBr}_2\text{-DMSO/DMF}$ (labelled in figure [73]) crystalline phases are detected. Finally, in addition to perovskite α -phase, a small contribution from δ -phase is observed in both intermediates.

A comparison between the relative crystalline contributions of the different phases in the pristine intermediates (see Table 1s) revealed that perovskite crystallinity is dominant in the P1 intermediate (83%) and less significant for the PTAA sample (48%). Indeed, the overall crystallinity associated to the precursor phases ($\text{PbI}_2 + \text{FABr-PbBr}_2\text{-DMSO/DMF}$) is significantly higher for the PTAA terminated sample than for the P1 one (51% vs 15%), with the strongest contribution deriving from the PbI_2 phase, as also confirmed by evaluation of the $I(\text{PbI}_2)/I(\alpha\text{-perovskite})$ intensity ratios reported in Table 2. These considerations are further supported by additional measurements performed on the intermediate samples deposited on Glass/ITO. The results of these analyses, presented in the supplementary material (figure 8s and Table 2s), confirm the trends observed in the pristine intermediates on PET, further supporting the correlation between the crystalline contribution of the different phases and the presence of PTAA or P1 as the topmost layer.

Upon neutron irradiation of the intermediates the persistence of a prevalent α -phase character can be observed for both intermediates. A decrease of perovskite α -phase crystallinity (in %) and an increase of PbI_2 crystallinity (in %) is observed upon irradiation of the samples (see Table 1s and Table 2), with a contextual increase of δ -phase contribution, which is more pronounced for PTAA than P1 terminated sample, as confirmed by evaluation of δ -phase/ α -phase intensity ratios reported in Table 3s. XRR and AFM measurements performed on the intermediates allowed shedding light on

the morphological changes occurring at the surface/interfaces after neutron irradiation of the samples. Interestingly, while the joint surface/interface average roughness evaluated by XRR resulted essentially unchanged after neutron bombardment of P1 intermediate, a decrease from 17.7 Å to 15.6 Å was deduced in the case of the PTAA terminated sample (Figure 9s). On the contrary, the surface roughness estimated by AFM analysis (Figure 10s) is essentially unaffected by neutron irradiation, regardless of the chemical nature of the HTL, thus suggesting that the morphological changes deduced by XRR after irradiation of PTAA sample can be mostly attributed to the PVK/PTAA interface. Importantly, XRD characterizations were also performed on the PTAA and P1 based complete staks (

Figure 4), providing insights on the effects of irradiation on the structural properties of perovskite devices. In addition to the contribution from perovskite α -phase (black circles), PbI_2 (black triangles) and $\text{FABr-PbBr}_2\text{-DMSO/DMF}$ (black asterisks), all the complete samples show strong XRD signals attributed to Au (111) and Au (200) reflections.

Interestingly, differently from the intermediate samples, the XRD patterns of the pristine cells do not show any contribution from δ -phase, thus suggesting the stabilizing effect of Au electrodes, which limit the formation of δ -phase in the pristine cells. It is thus reasonable to conclude that δ -phase is formed in the pristine intermediate as a consequence of structural degradation of the perovskite film occurring after its direct exposure to environmental moisture conditions.[74] [75]

Comparison of the XRD pattern collected before and after neutron irradiation generally confirmed the persistence of α -phase perovskite for both type of cells. Remarkably, different behaviour can be observed depending on the HTL, as shown by the evaluation of crystallinity percentage (Table 4s) and $I(\text{PbI}_2)/I(\alpha\text{-perovskite})$ intensity ratios (Table 2 and Table 2s): while irradiation of the PTAA cell induces a strong decrease in the crystallinity associated to perovskite α -phase (coupled with a significant increase in the % crystallinity of PbI_2), when the P1 cell is considered, such degradation effects are strongly inhibited independently of the substrate.

The above observations, together with the results obtained for the intermediate samples, suggest that P1 based devices show improved structural stability than PTAA.

Overall, the improved resilience of P1 devices could be tentatively rationalized considering the quite different molecular structure between the two HTLs. Firstly the high MW of PTAA, albeit ensuring better efficiency, lacks for a complete coverage of the perovskite active layer leading to higher ratio of precursors especially PbI_2 which are defective, even on freshly fabricated samples. [76] Additionally the presence of conjugated (i.e. electron rich) sulfur and nitrogen atoms which can act as Lewis Bases,[77] [78] allow an effectively coordination of Pb(II) moieties by donating their electron lone pairs, [79][80] thus minimising the PbI_2 formation. On the other hand, the unconjugated and relatively more sterically hindered nitrogen atom of PTAA could hardly play the role of a Lewis Base, giving rise to a more evident PbI_2 formation. Simultaneously, after irradiation, PTAA samples experience a further decrease of the percentage of crystalline perovskite α -phase (from 62% to 39%) meanwhile when P1 is used the crystalline α -phase perovskite is retained at a much higher quantity (90% to 88%), further suggesting the incomplete protection of the active layer which is more prone to react with external agents. These results suggest how when designing hole transporting materials for space applications, the search for high efficiency could not be decoupled from the development of stable polymeric materials able to also play the role of a protective film of the active layer.

Table 2: PbI_2/α -perovskite intensity ratios as obtained from XRD measurements carried out on the complete/intermediate devices on PET before/after irradiation.

	I(PbI_2/α-perovskite)			
	Intermediate device		Complete device	
	Pristine	After irradiation	Pristine	After irradiation
PTAA	1.04 ± 0.06	1.15 ± 0.06	0.51 ± 0.04	1.46 ± 0.06
P1	0.13 ± 0.02	0.24 ± 0.02	0.05 ± 0.03	0.08 ± 0.02

Figure 4: XRD patterns collected upon (A) PTAA and (B) P1 complete cells in the pristine state (black plots) and after irradiation (red plots).

3. Conclusion

The resilience of flexible perovskite solar cells under atmospheric neutron irradiation (fluence of $5 \cdot 10^9$ n/cm²) is investigated for potential space applications of such devices. We compare the performance of two classes of polymeric hole transport materials, namely an in-house synthesized polymer (P1) and a commercial one (PTAA). The P1-based devices show no PCE loss (+2% increment), whereas the PTAA-based counterparts still retain 80% of their initial PCE. The resilience toward atmospheric neutrons is also evident looking at the short-circuit current measures. Indeed, while P1 devices show little difference between the irradiated and control samples, neutron-aged PTAA devices retain a lesser portion of J_{SC} than the controls. A similar trend is observed on light-dependant J_{SC} measures, suggesting that the performance of our f-PSCs is mostly affected by charge extraction losses. More interestingly, the open circuit voltage of all samples remains stable across all devices, corroborated by QFLS maps, implying that atmospheric neutron irradiation does not substantially increase the levels of nonradiative recombination in these devices.

Structural and morphological analysis has shown overall good stability of the perovskite bulk, as well as high resilience of the P1-based devices in the perovskite/HTL interface. For the PTAA counterparts

on the other hand, the perovskite/HTL interface exhibits a reduction in roughness as well as an increase in unreacted PbI_2 content. Our results evidence a dramatic effect stemming from the chemical nature of the polymeric HTL on the performance of neutron-aged devices. Further studies are currently ongoing focusing on tailoring the structural backbone of P1 (*e.g.* to increase its planarity) toward a more resilient structure.

4. Experimental

The triple cation perovskite solution was prepared by weighing 19.5 mg of CsI (TCI), 21.6 mg of MABr (GreatCell Solar Materials), 87.2 mg of PbBr_2 (TCI), 166.1 mg of FAI (Greatcell Solar Materials), and 547.4 mg of PbI_2 (TCI) for 1 mL of solution, and dissolved in 760 mL of DMF and 240 mL of DMSO (both anhydrous, Sigma-Aldrich). For the HTL solutions, 12 mg of 100 kDa PTAA (Solaris Chem) was dissolved in 1 mL of toluene (anhydrous, Sigma-Aldrich), and 12 mg of P1 was dissolved in 1 mL of THF (anhydrous, Sigma-Aldrich). The P1 polymer was synthesized in house as described in our previous work.[51] All solutions were left stirring for 12 hours. Once fully dissolved, the P1 and PTAA solutions were doped by adding 5.6 μL of 4-tert-butylpyridine (Sigma-Aldrich) and 10.5 μL of bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (lithium salts) dissolved in acetonitrile (171 mg/mL) for each mL of HTL solution. The doped solutions were then left stirring for 1 hour.

To fabricate the devices, PET/ITO ($15 \Omega/\square$) substrates were laser patterned to define four isolated cells on a $25 \cdot 25 \text{ mm}^2$ area, and cleaned in an ultrasonic bath in, sequentially, isopropanol and water for 20 minutes for each solvent. The substrates were then dried and attached to a $25 \cdot 25 \text{ mm}^2$ rigid glass substrate via silicon adhesive (Smooth-on Ecoflex 00-50), to ensure the samples remain flat throughout the entire fabrication. The samples were left in a UV-Ozone chamber for 10 minutes; immediately afterwards, an aqueous dispersion of SnO_2 (15% wt, Alpha Aesar) was spin coated at 6000 rpm for 35 s, and subsequently annealed on a hotplate at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 minutes. The samples were then once again treated in a UV-Ozone chamber for 20 minutes, and swiftly brought in a glovebox in N_2 atmosphere. The perovskite solution was spin coated at 1000 rpm for 10 s followed by 30 sec at 5000 rpm. As antisolvent, 150 μL of anhydrous chlorobenzene (Sigma-Aldrich) was dripped 7 s before the end of the second step, followed by annealing of the samples at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 hour. After cooling the samples, either the P1 or PTAA solution was spin coated at 1500 rpm for 30 s (dynamic deposition). Finally, 100 nm of gold were thermally evaporated.

4.1 Device Characterization

The photovoltaic performance of the devices was estimated by recording current density-voltage (JV) scans at a scan rate of $200 \text{ mV} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ with a Sun 2000 (Abet Technologies) xenon lamp sun simulator under simulated air mass 1.5G, and an acquisition set-up provided by Cicci Research, calibrated with a reference silicon cell (Rera solutions).

Hyperspectral photoluminescence microscopy measurements were performed on a widefield optical microscope equipped with a Photon etc. IMA system, 20x objective (Nikon TU Plan Fluor 20x/0.45), and CMOS camera (Hamamatsu ORCA-Flash4.0 V3). Imaging was performed from the film side

opposite the substrate, through a Kapton encapsulating layer used to minimize environmental exposure. Large-area illumination from fiber-coupled 530 nm and 617 nm LEDs (Thorlabs) both driven at a current of 1 A was used to provide reproducible and uniform excitation over the field of view. Scattered excitation was removed from the PL signal with a dichroic mirror (Semrock 664 nm longpass, BLP01-664R-25). The system is calibrated for absolute-intensity measurements by sequential measurement of a radiometrically calibrated halogen lamp and a 675 nm laser at a known power (see [81] for details). Quasi-Fermi level splitting values were obtained by fitting absolute-intensity PL spectra to the generalized Planck equation, using sub-bandgap absorption models and fitting methods established by Katahara and Hillhouse [82] [83] (see supplementary note 1 for details).

Intensity dependent J_{sc} and V_{oc} were estimated using a commercial All-in-One measuring set-up (Arkeo-Ariadne, provided by Ciccì Research), using the white LEDs integrated in the measurement set-up, and measuring the performance of our cells at illuminations up to 3 suns, for 10 linearly increasing intensity levels, performing a JV scan at each level.

XRD and XRR measurements were carried out by a Panalytical Empyrean X-ray diffractometer equipped with a Cu-anode X-ray source (K-Alpha1 [\AA] = 1.54060; K-Alpha2 [\AA] = 1.54443) and a flat sample holder for thin film characterization. For all the measurements, generator parameters were kept fixed at 45 mA and 40 kV and detection was accomplished by means of a PixCel 3D detector working in linear mode.

XRD patterns were collected in Bragg-Brentano configuration in the angular 2θ range 5° - 70° (Gonio acquisition, Step Size [$^\circ 2\theta$] = 0.0260, Scan Type: Continuous) setting incident optical pathways by divergent slits (Divergence Slit Type Fixed, Divergence Slit Size [$^\circ$] = 0.2177).

XRR measurements were performed in the angular range 0.03° - 2° (2θ acquisition, Step Size [$^\circ 2\theta$] = 0.002, Scan Type: continuous) setting incident optical pathways by divergent slits (Divergence Slit Type Fixed, Divergence Slit Size [$^\circ$] = 0.0286 and the diffracted beam path by a parallel plate collimator (opening [$^\circ$] = 0.27).

Morphological surface characteristics of the samples were investigated using an in house developed Atomic Force Microscope (AFM), equipped with a $30\ \mu\text{m} \times 30\ \mu\text{m}$ scanner. Several portions of the samples were monitored in non-contact mode by means of ultrasharp gold coated non-contact AFM probes (NT-MDT). Images ranging from 30×30 to $10 \times 10\ \mu\text{m}$ (500 points/image) were collected.

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